

INTRODUCTION OF MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: the article outlines important strategic goals, such as the widespread use of modern, information, digital technologies in enterprises and organizations that are important today, and ensuring their competitiveness in the world.

Key words: IT, electronic data, foreign investors, Videoconferencing, Immediate feedback, social networking, electronic communication,

Introduction. Information technologies is the use of computers to create, process, store, retrieve, and exchange all kinds of electronic data and information. IT is typically used within the context of business operations as opposed to personal or entertainment technologies. IT forms part of information and communication technology. IT involves many things. Take, for instance, an IT department in a company. There are many people with many jobs and varied responsibilities. These responsibilities range from keeping systems and data secure to keeping networks up and running. There are people who input data, people who manage databases and people who do programming.

Research methodology. The purpose of the research is to draw scientific conclusions for the development of scientific and practical proposals and recommendations based on the results of the analysis of the practice of ensuring the active penetration of information and communication technologies. Theoretical and methodological basis of this article are conclusions, suggestions and recommendations based on general economic literature and scientific articles, analysis of research in the field of IT by economists and technologists, expert

evaluation, process observation, systematic approach to economic events and processes.

The results of analysis and discussion. The competitiveness of national economies, the convenience of the state for domestic and foreign investors in many respects depends on the advanced level of information services. National sources of information have become one of the most important components of economic and social development, which increasingly determines the level of global competitiveness of individual countries. Especially the role of information technology in the modern market economy. It is known that without the effective use of information, which is the product of human science, it is impossible to develop society, accelerate science and technology, increase the efficiency of production. Therefore, the field of information is one of the main factors in the development of science and technology, the economy.

At the present time the rate of growth of information flows is so high that it is becoming increasingly difficult to process them in the old ways. Therefore, many scientific articles and special literature discuss the issues of informatization of society, the development of information resources, the creation of new technologies of information processing, their effective use. One of the main factors influencing scientific and technological progress in all spheres of human activity is the widespread use of new information technologies. Informatization of society is one of the most important problems in the world, a set of vital problems of human development, the development of modern science.

World experience confirms the positive impact of information and communication technologies on the socio-economic development of the country. Full use of the huge potential of information and communication technologies sets priorities for the implementation of comprehensive economic reforms involving business, individuals and society as a whole, as ICT is actively entering the lives and activities of individuals and infrastructure in all its aspects. One of the reasons for

the success of the economies of developed countries is that they always have high access to fast and accurate information. Studies show that managers spend 29% of their working time on intellectual work and use the rest 71% inefficiently.

Uses of Information Technology in Business

- Product Development;
- Globalization;
- Facilitate Fast Payment Transfer;
- Efficient and Effective Storage;
- Ease of Communication;
- Competitive Advantage Over Competitors.

Information technology benefits everyone personally, from the way you shop to the way you gather information. It plays an important role in organizations, too, streamlining processes and keeping your business connected and running smoothly.

The advantages of IT as they affect your business:

- Increased Data Security. It has forever changed the way businesses store files. It is safer to store information in a secure computer database than to leave it in physical files. Your business will have some level of protection from lawsuits stemming from data breaches if it is proven that it has taken the appropriate cybersecurity measures;
- Information Technology can help your business save money. It can increase productivity by streamlining processes. Routine reports and tasks that would traditionally require manual research and documentation are available at the click of a mouse. IT will save money on postage. Seems a simple concept, but the old days of physical mailers are a thing of the past. Email is faster and more efficient than standard postal solutions. It saves money by simplifying, migrating, and outsourcing high price functions such as payroll, supply chain purchases, and even customer support;

- Information Technology benefits communication. You can communicate with customers and prospective clients via social media and targeted ads, and, thanks to information technology, you can sell your products to a much wider audience than ever before;
- Improved Productivity. Your workplace will see the advantages of information technology in increased productivity and efficiency. These advantages include: instant access to files, Immediate feedback on collaborative projects, Videoconferencing and real time communication, Project management tools, Do-it-yourself portals for payroll, password management, and more, Automated processes and data analysis, Faster results and faster task resolution.;
- A Wider Talent Net is One of the Biggest Advantages of Information Technology. If there's one thing businesses have learned, it's that remote work is the face of the modern workplace. Remote work is an information technology advantage all its own, but it has even wider implications. Your talent pool just got a lot deeper;
- Achieving Coordination and Uniformity. With informational technology, tasks can be organized, coordinated, and uniform. It's far easier to follow procedure when there is a procedure, and information technology provides a framework for tasks and projects that everyone on the team can follow.

One aspect of technology that has had a great impact on society is how it affects learning. It's made learning more interactive and collaborative, this helps people better engage with the material that they are learning and have trouble with. Also, it gets you better access to resources. With the creation of the internet, it gives us access to information at a twenty-four-hour rate and you have access to almost anything online. In addition, it allows students to get work done easier. Students can take quizzes and exams more easily, and teachers being able to hold online classes can very effective. It also expands the boundaries of the classroom, encouraging self-

paced learning. People can access learning through YouTube and social media. This helps students learn better than sitting down for lectures and reading from textbooks. These technological advancements made learning more fun and convenient. Another way technology has impacted society is through communication, how we talk and communicate with one another worldwide. Technology brought many new methods of electronic communication. For example, there are emails, social networking, you can facetime a person that lives on the other side of the world, and here's video conferencing where you can have conferences electronically.

Table 1

The three Varieties of Work-Changing IT¹

IT Category	Definition	Characteristics	Examples
Function IT	IT that assists with the execution of discrete tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be adopted without complements; • Impact increases when complement are in place. 	Simulators, spreadsheets, computer-aided design, and statistical software
Network IT	IT that facilitates interactions without specifying their parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doesn't impose complements but lets them emerge over time; • Doesn't specify tasks or sequences; • Accepts data in many formats; • Use is optional. 	e-mail, instant messaging, blogs
Enterprise IT	IT that specifies business processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imposes complements throughout the organization; • Defines tasks and sequences; • Mandates data formats; 	Software for enterprise resource planning, customer resource

¹Mastering the Three Worlds of Information Technology. Harvard Business Review.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use is mandatory 	management, and supply chain management
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Conclusions and suggestions. In short, it is impossible to imagine our lives without digital technology. Important processes such as digitization, innovation, modernization, diversification are taking place in all industries and sectors, enterprises and organizations. Today, information systems are becoming an integral part of the organization. Today, many executives have identified the need for knowledge in the field of information systems in order to develop and sustain the organization. Information systems lead to the expansion and development of the company through the opening of branches in different regions, the introduction of new products and services, changes in the nature of workplaces and production processes, as well as radical changes in the way of doing business.

Prospects for further strengthening of innovative digital information and communication technologies are primarily related to increasing the volume of foreign investment in the country. The introduction of state-of-the-art information technologies by developed countries with foreign investment will certainly lead to promising results in all areas.

The inflow of foreign investment in turn requires highly educated professionals. Qualification of scientific personnel also contributes to the development of information technologies. Improving the media literacy of citizens, explaining to them the enormous advantages of technology, that is, the use of new technologies will increase productivity and efficient use of time.

Information Technologies helps businesses, governments, and individuals increase their efficiency and effectiveness. Rapid improvements in hardware and processing ability forces consumers to purchase new, relevant technology. On a market level,

this rapid turnover creates demand. From a firm's perspective however, this can result in a lower customer retention rate. Concludes that under certain conditions, information and communication technologies can significantly enhance poor people's human and social capabilities and have a positive impact on their well-being. Communication for technology provides those who have communication challenges a way of expressing their wants and needs. People of all ages and abilities can use and benefit from using communication technology.

- ICT is redefining the economic, social and cultural scene;
- The impact of ICT is much more and further reaching than any other technology invented so far;
- ICT is empowering society in both the economic and social contexts;
- Digital Divide is increasing among and within nations;
- The Government should recognize that communication and knowledge are two intertwined success factors;
- New challenges for governance and institutions because of new issues.

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